

Appendix IV

Weights (values) assigned by stakeholders to goals

Stakeholders	Goals	Weights
S1: Advertiser S2: User	G1: Send messages to all pages' followers G2: Delete advertising messages	G1. S1: 2; S2: 4 G2. S1: 5; S2: 3
S1: Advertiser S2: Government	G3: Track people's data G4: Prevent all kinds of fraud and Be in charge of all the chatbots, or other automatic functions within the messenger	G3. S1: 1; S2: 1 G4. S1: 5; S2: 3
S1: Advertiser S2: Advertiser	G5: Create individual ads G6: Use the same ads for all users	G5. S1: 3; S2: 3 G6. S1: 5; S2: 2
S1: Advertiser S2: Government	G7: Target non-brand-aware users G8: Restrict advertisers from doing extensive targeting	G7. S1: 1; S2: 5 G8. S1: 5; S2: 2
S1: Advertiser S2: User	G9: Host webinars/online events G10: Want the app to be as basic as possible	G9. S1: 1; S2: 2 G10. S1: 1; S2: 1
S1: Advertiser S2: User S3: User	G11: Avoid ad blockers G12: Block ads while playing games G13: Filter ads	G11. S1: 1; S2: 5; S3: 5 G12. S1: 5; S2: 2; S3: 3 G13. S1: 4; S2: 1; S3: 4
S1: Advertiser S2: Government	G14: Impact people's choices G15: Impact people's choices	G14. S1: 1; S2: 3 G15. S1: 4; S2: 1
S1: Advertiser S2: Government	G16: Create a “circle” of customers to chat with G17: Move messages from 3rd parties to spam folder	G16. S1: 1; S2: 3 G17. S1: 4; S2: 1
S1: User S2: Government S3: Government	G18: Have secret chats G19: Listen to all voice messages G20: Read all the messages from all chats	G18. S1: 1; S2: 5; S3: 5 G19. S1: 3; S2: 1; S3: 1 G20. S1: 5; S2: 1; S3: 1
S1: User S2: Government	G21: Edit stories G22: See all messages/stories and etc. which have been edited	G21. S1: 1; S2: 5 G22. S1: 3; S2: 1
S1: User S2: User S3: Government	G23: Play all kinds of games and Integrate all browser games G24: Remove gaming feature G25: Restrict some games	G23. S1: 1; S2: 3; S3: 4 G24. S1: 5; S2: 1; S3: 3 G25. S1: 5; S2: 1; S3: 1
S1: User S2: Government	G26: Restrict some people from seeing any information related to me G27: Get all the detailed information about the person	G26. S1: 1; S2: 3 G27. S1: 1; S2: 5
S1: User S2: User	G28: Delete others’ messages G29: Constrain others from deleting my messages	G28. S1: 1; S2: 3 G29. S1: 5; S2: 1